

THE DEVELOPMENT, GROWTH AND MANAGEMENT OF TERTIARY INSTITUTION IN NIGERIA.

By

OLAYIWOLA, S. A. & BUHARI, A. I.

*Agricultural Science Education Department Technical
Education Department Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin.*

Abstract

Tertiary institutions are post-secondary educational establishments. This paper examines how the tertiary institutions can be managed and developed with laws binding the organs of the universities. The purpose of higher education is to acquire, develop and inculcate the proper value-orientation for the survival of individuals and the society, and also to promote national unity. The management cannot be handled by an individual or group of members without the intervention of government. It is recommended that the issue of funds needs to be addressed objectively, sincerely and decisively for the survival of the university, which can be achieved by providing effective leaders through the intervention of Federal government.

Key words: *Development, growth, management and tertiary institution*

Introduction

Tertiary institutions are post-secondary educational establishments where higher education is offered. They include universities, polytechnics, colleges of technology, colleges of education, correspondence colleges and similar colleges that provide higher education facilities (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1989).

This paper examines what a university is, a short history of the introduction of university, purpose of university education, thereafter; discusses the management of universities, organization and hierarchy of authority, discipline control of services and exercise of autonomy. The Oxford

Advanced Learner's Dictionary (9th Edition) defines a university as an educational institution at the highest level of education where one can study for a degree or do research.

History of the Introduction of University and Tertiary Institutions

The genesis of university education in Nigeria is traceable to the Elliot Commission of 1943 instituted by the British Government and the Eric Ashby Commission on post secondary and higher education of 1959 instituted by the Nigerian Government. The Elliot Commission resulted in the establishment of the University College, Ibadan. Between 1948 and 1959, the University College Ibadan, a College of the University of London was the only tertiary institution in the country. After Ibadan, the first established, the University the University of Nigeria, Nsukka was established in 1960 by the government of Eastern Region at that time, (Karibi Whyte, 2010).

In 1962, three more universities were established at Lagos, Zaria and Ile-Ife by the Federal Government and Governments of Northern and Western Regions of Nigeria respectively. These are the Lagos, Ahmadu Bello, and Obafemi Awolowo Universities respectively. In the same year 1962 the University College Ibadan became the University of Ibadan; Ahmadu Bello and Obafemi Awolowo Universities were established from the former Colleges of Arts and Sciences at Zaria and Ibadan respectively. In 1972, the Midwest Institute of Technology, Benin City was converted into a university, now the University of Benin. It is fair to observe that the government of Eastern Region of Nigeria under Lt. Col. Odumegwu Ojukwu, the Military Governor of Eastern Region of Nigeria had earlier in 1967 established a University of Technology in Port Harcourt in an effort to implement the recommendation of Ashby Report of 1959. Sir Eric Ashby had in the report of his commission on higher education recommended the establishment of a technological institute in Port Harcourt with bias for petrochemical studies

(Karibi Whyte, 2010). The implementation of the efforts was vitiated by the Nigerian civil war 1967-1970.

Apart from political considerations of the economy, it has always been recognized that education is the bedrock of and the veritable tool for achieving goals in national development, economic growth, social and intellectual emancipation of the individual. It has been identified as the most potent and powerful instrument for social regeneration and reform. Hence as more states were created in the federation, the government of such states embarked on the establishment of universities in order to realize their dreams about the development of the much needed man power and to cater for their peculiar needs in terms of peculiar ecology.

The general expectation of Nigerian governments is that higher education provided by the universities, is the veritable fountain of intellectual power which can be harnessed for the social economic development of the nation. Thus university education is designed for the production of highly skilled and knowledgeable citizenry for the development and acceleration of national human and material resources.

The Purpose of University Education

The purpose of higher education is very aptly stated in the Education Act, Rivers State University of Science and Technology, (RSUST) (2002).

These are:

- i. The acquisition, development and inculcation of the proper value-orientation for the survival of individuals and the society.
- ii. The development of the intellectual capacities of individuals to understand and appreciate their environment.
- iii. The acquisition of both physical and intellectual skill to enable individuals to develop into useful members of the community.
- iv. The acquisition of an objective view of local and external environment.

- v. The promotion and encouragement of scholarship and research.
- vi. Making of an optimum contribution to national development through the training of higher level manpower.
- vii. The promotion of national unity by ensuring that the admission of students and recruitment of staff into universities and other institutions of higher learning shall as far as possible be on a broad national basis.

In summary the purpose of tertiary institution is to achieve the tripartite objective of national, political integration of the disparate ethnic nationalities and national economic development by improving the skills for the economy and the social and intellectual development of the citizenry. The level and status of a country's education is considered with the index of its social political growth and identified by its economic status.

Management of Tertiary Institutions

The management of a tertiary institution cannot be handled by an individual or group of members without the intervention of government. The management is vested in the principal organs which are stated in their enabling status. These organs are the council of university, the senate, the congregation and the convocation.

The council and the senate are concerned with the day to day administration of the institution. For the good management and development of the university, the hierarchy of authority and exercise of management power in the enabling statuses are:

- A Chancellor
- Pro-chancellor and a Council
- A Vice-chancellor and the Senate
- A body to be called the congregation
- A body to be called the Convocation

The Council is the governing body of the university and the employer of

all its staff. It is responsible for the condition of service, welfare, discipline, development and growth of the university. The law allows the Council to accept funds from Alumni Association and private sector contributions; voluntary agencies and philanthropic organizations and individuals. The Council is allowed to raise funds by loans on the security of university property. All these are in addition to the necessary funding provided by the Education Tax Fund and the Petroleum Development Fund.

The Senate

The senate of the university shall consists of:

- a) The Vice-Chancellor and the Deputy Vice-Chancellor(s)
- b) Deans of the various faculties
- c) The Professors
- d) The Librarian
- e) At least two senior lecturers or teachers from each college as may be elected to be determined by the senate
- f) The persons for the time being hold such appointments on the staff of the university as may be specified by the Vice-Chancellor.

The senate in addition to teaching, admission of students into the university is empowered to make provision for the establishment, organization and control of campuses, colleges, faculties, institutes, schools, extra-mural departments and other teaching and research facilities and responsibility for the different branches of learning.

ii. The senate is also responsible for supervision of the welfare of students and regulations of their conduct.

iii. The award of degree and diploma, regular or honorary.

However, this provision is contradicted by the powers of JAMB which provides for the determination of minimum entry requirements into all universities. The universities by the exercise of the powers and functions of

the senate and in the exercise of academic autonomy should be free to prescribe additional requirement within the national guidelines. This they have done and is consistent with the exercise by the senate of their statutory power and autonomy in respect of admission of students. One of the anxieties of university administration is the accreditation exercise of the programmes of faculties and the establishment of minimum standards. The random selection by the National Universities Commission of inspectors once every five years to report on the accreditation of programmes is not only undesirable but also unsatisfactory.

The credibility of the accreditation will be better assured if done in collaboration with established recognized professional bodies with National University Commission (NUC), (University of Ibadan Act, 2003).

In view of developing a university and managing the same institution, there must be a law while creating universities which binds the council and senates, specific disciplinary powers over members of council, employees of the university and students.

The exercise may arise from misconduct or inability to perform the functions of office or employment in the case of members of council and members of staff. In addition disciplinary action may be instituted against any member of staff for good cause which has been defined to mean; "Gross misconduct or inability to discharge the functions of his office arising from infirmity of body or mind", (University miscellaneous provision, 2003).

As in the case of students misconduct as a ground for discipline, the use of violence whether alone or in conspiracy with others for the purpose of achieving redress of grievance on the campus is a grand case of misconduct. The law has also provided for the procedure in the ascertainment and determination of guilt in each case. The statute clearly provides for a hearing of the person alleged to have offended.

A member of the council may be removed on the recommendation of

the council to the Governor or president as the case might be through the commissioner or minister. The Governor or the president is expected to make inquiries about the complaint and will only approve the recommendations if satisfied. The commissioner or the minister is required to serve the member affected with the recommendation for his removal.

On the academic and administrative staff, the procedure involved in disciplining any member is more elaborate. The general reason of misconduct or inability to perform the function of office or employment also applies.

The council elected by the Government will give notice to the person in question of the reasons for his suspension, afford him opportunity to make representations in person to the council on the matter. On the request of the member of staff, or any three members of a council, a joint committee of council and senate will be constituted within a month from the notice to investigate the matter and report to council. The member of staff will be afforded opportunity to appear before the committee. A person so suspended if found guilty shall be on half pay, the council shall come to decision on such matter within three (3) months of such suspension, (University of Ibadan Act, 2003).

However, the decision whether to continue the suspension or not or on what term, to reinstate the person or terminate his appointment or consider whatever lesser disciplinary action to be taken must be taken within 3 months. Again the council shall before the expiration of three months from such a decision come to a final determination of the case concerning such person (Garba, 1986).

Discipline of Students

Where a student by himself or in conspiracy with others uses violence for the purpose of achieving a redress or an advantage on the campus of the university, the exercise of this power enables the Vice-Chancellor to restrict

the student from participation in the activities of the university or use such facilities of the school as may be specified. The student may be rusticated for such period as may be specified or may be expected, (Garba, 1986).

In cases involving rustication or expulsion, the student has a right of appeal to the Council which would inquire into the matter and may either confirm, set aside or modify the sentence imposed by the Vice-Chancellor.

The Governing Council is one of the principal organs of the university, by the law, it has the general control and superintendence of the policy, finances and property of the university including its public relations, specifically vested in the Governing Council of the university is the function of the employment of all staff of the university.

Concisely stated, the council of the university is the employer of all the staff of the university. All appointment of staff are made by or on the authority of the Governing Council on the recommendation of the appointment and promotion committee, (Laoye, 1990).

Letter of appointment from the employer, that is, the Council of the university is issued by the Registrar as a Secretary to the Council or an authorized member of the university administration acting on his behalf, (Brown, 1929).

Similarly, the contract between the university and the employee are; tenure of appointment; temporary appointment; part-time appointment; and contract appointment.

At this juncture, it should be noted that the relationship between the university and its staff is that of contract of service. The relationship is generally regarded and known in law as that of master and servant, the university being the master and the employee the servant. At common law, a contract between a master and his servant may be terminated at any time by the master, even without giving any reason for so doing, (Karibi Whyte, 2010).

However, where there is a written contract of services prescribing the terms and conditions of services, the master can only validly terminate the contract in the conditions stipulated in such contract.

The university and its councils are both a creation of statutes. They accordingly can only act validly within and under the powers conferred on them by the relevant statutes.

However in Nigeria, public servants in the established and pensionable cadre of the government services do not hold their offices at the pleasure of the Government. Rather, their appointments are based upon rules and regulations memoranda of appointment governing such offices, (Adebayo, 2000).

There is now the view as agreed in the negotiation with the unions that in addition a member of the Governing Council of a university should be a holder of a regular university degree (as opposed to an honorary degree), (Miscellaneous provision amendment, 2003).

The amendment of 2007 provides for a tenure of 4 years from inauguration, subject to dissolution on the ground of incompetence and corruption in the council. Again, section 2M protects the exercise of the statutory powers of the council from establishment circulars inconsistent with the exercise of such powers. They shall not apply to the universities. The council is designed to be free and independent in the exercise of its responsibilities and in the discharge of its duties for the effective and efficient management and growth and development of the universities, (Miscellaneous provision amendment, 2007).

It has now been agreed in the negotiation with the unions of workers that no acting principal officer shall stay in office in that capacity for more than six months. The council has power to remove the Deputy Vice-Chancellor for good cause acting on the recommendation of the Vice Chancellor.

The law has provided for the composition and powers of the senate and protects the interference with the exercise by the senate of their powers where these are in accordance with their enabling statutes. The senate is empowered by the statutes in all academic matters to organize and control teaching and research, admission of students, award of degrees and diplomas including honorary degrees, promotion of research and exercise of other functions in accordance with the laws and statutes of the university. The optimum exercise of some of these statutory power would appear to be affected by other legal provisions. For instance, the power to admit students is affected by the provision of the JAMB Act which empowers JAMB to prescribe and determine minimum qualification for matriculation and admission into universities.

The interposition of the post UME test after publication of JAMB result since 2005 is the design of the universities to enforce compliance with their standards to students offered admission into their universities.

The senate which has the final authority in academic matters including regulation of admission should have the power to administer further test as a requirement of the screening process.

The validity of post UME test which was introduced by ministerial directive is suspect. It is necessary to safeguard the autonomy of universities and powers of the senate over admission in all academic matters and to avoid vesting JAMB with unqualified power to place students, (Karibi Whyte, 2010 and Idris, 2010)

Lastly, the release of block money by the Federal Government to NUC for onward disbursement to the university is unnecessary. The money should be given directly to each university to disburse the grants directly to the council.

Conclusion

It is sufficient for the purpose of this paper to summarise by observing the truism that university being a creation of the law, the realization of fundamental objectives of aspiration of the country and its citizenry will better be satisfied by the scrupulous observance of the provision of the statutes.

The country is poised on achieving its set out programmes of economic and political goals. It is difficult to disagree with submission of academic staff union of universities to the Re-negotiation Committee on the Repositioning of the Universities for better effect that:

- i. The key to the survival of our country on the 21st century lies in our country's ability to produce applied and theoretical knowledge in science, technology and humanities; and
- ii. The task of vitalizing and accelerating the development of the Nigerian universities into one of the best in world cannot be delayed (more so, if Nigeria is to become one of the leading economies in the world as desired by the government).

A revitalized management of our universities in the scrupulous observance and exercise of their statutory powers uninhibited by political consideration and legal implements, the unrestricted exercise of their autonomy and academic freedom are the fulcrum upon which the growth and development of the country in the 21st century will be based.

The struggle for the autonomy of the university and of academic freedom has been long, arduous and continuous. Considerable inroads have been made on both fronts by the amendments referred to.

Until all the laws encroaching on the exercise of university autonomy have been reviewed and repealed, the realization of the goals of university education will continue to elude the country.

Recommendations

1. The issue of fund needs to be addressed objectively, sincerely and decisively for the survival of the university.
2. The Federal Government must provide the effective leadership.
3. The state government and private sectors must take a queue and not do less for their universities.
4. The laws binding the council, senate and employees of the institutions must be stood by and when necessary it should be revised so as to suit any present conditions of the institution. 08033441907

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